

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Evaluating the watershed characteristics influence on the flood vulnerability of Barsa River basin to Industrial area, Pasakha-Bhutan

Leki Dorji*

*Civil Engineering and Engineering Geology Department, College of Science and Technology, Royal University of Bhutan

Corresponding Author Email: ldorjee6722@gmail.com

Received: 13 July 2021 / Revised: 27 July 2021 / Accepted: 14 August 2021

Published online: 1 September 2021

Abstract

Bhutan has been poised to be a complicated rugged terrain country where hydrology requires effective utilization of different types of hydrological databases. Accordingly, better management of floods/drought events and understanding of rainfall-runoff phenomenon based on past hydrological data becomes necessary. However, hydrologically complicated features leading to one of the main causes of erratic data assets for a country like Bhutan facing myriads of challenges to take appropriate decisions. This study attempts to estimate the surface runoff from the ungauged Barsa (River) basin and also to estimate the discharge from the moraine dam based on the record data. Pasakha is an industrial hub posing most vulnerable to flood during the monsoon seasons due to high precipitation and the formation of an artificial lake upstream of the river. Hence, HEC-HMS 3.4 has been adopted to prepare the Hydrological Soil Group (HSG) map and Land-use map of the area. HSG map has been mapped by performing numerous standard infiltration tests throughout the basin to get the infiltration rate at each basin. To obtain a better result, the interpolating process was completed by employing the Geostatistical Kriging interpolation method in ArcGIS. Land use map has been prepared by using Toposheet 78F05 (1:50,000), Phuentsholing base map (CAD data), and recent Google images. Rainfall data for the year (2013-2019) were acquired from Metrological Department. HSG map and Land use maps were used as feed data in HEC-HMS for simulation of surface runoff as discharge. For the modeling, the combined discharge of surface runoff and discharge estimated from an artificial moraine dam were fed in HEC-RAS 5.0. In this study, the Flood Plain Zoning (FPZ) has been generated for the hydraulic analysis to determine the flood arial expansion with estimated discharge. Thus, it is observed that 48.18 acres are affected in four critical designated areas during the peak flood.

Keywords: Rainfall-runoff modeling, SCS-CN method, HEC-HMS, ArcGIS, Interpolation

Introduction

An increase of developmental activities of rural land changing to urban land generally rises soil erosion and the amount of storm runoff volume in a particular watershed area (Cronshey et al., 1986). The development of an area reduces the rate of infiltration thereby growing peak discharge of the stormwater (Cronshey et al., 1986). Curve Number (CN) indicating the value of the index which signifies the complexity of soil-cover reflecting the response of a definite soil under certain to rainstorm water through runoff and infiltration (Elhakeem and Papanicolaou, 2009). However, the identification of the curve number value of the basin depends on the precise use of land use/cover map incorporating the hydrological soil groups (Tekeli et al., 2007). The method engaged for the evaluation of runoff perhaps to a small

watershed was the SCS process, which becomes a popular strategy for detecting the land uses and forested watershed area (Soulis et al., 2009). Geographical Information Systems (GIS) can be integrated with managing spatial databases and has been effective in identifying the different features of the study area with available images. It is also a useful tool for the management of spatial data and examining the related features of hydrological strategies (Dhawale, 2013). For the specific design, the simulation of the rainfall-runoff processes of the variant watershed, the Hydrological Modeling System (HMS) is significantly adopted.

It has been noticed that floods either by rainfall or lakes significantly change in magnitude causing adverse effects to natural environmental and man-made structures. These flooding events that are experienced throughout the world often lead to massive damages including economic losses such as business, infrastructure, and health care for the public (DMSG, 2001; Ikhuria et al., 2012). Flooding is a noticeable event which is considered as one of the most severe natural environmental hazards globally (Seyedeh et al., 2008), and it is also been recorded that about 40% of all deaths were triggered by natural disasters, mostly by the frequent flood actions more prevalent in developing countries. Aside from river flood, flash flooding is considered another serious natural hazard (Gruntfest and Handmer, 2001), and the rising of groundwater table also leads to flooding in soil/ground of certain nature (Burt et al., 2002) and some of the most prominent floods have been occurred due to breaches of a dams or artificial reservoirs (Forkuo, 2011). In recent years, the implementation of the hydraulic model of using Hydrologic Engineering Center- River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) with GIS software has been recommended as a solution to Flood Plain Zoning (FPZ).

The attempt of this study is, to achieve some of the following objectives of the study area, (a) Modelling of river using HEC-RAS with a combined discharge of surface runoff and the artificial moraine dam based on record data (b) Analysing the disaster impact on the physical and economic life and properties of the residents living along the river (c) Possible solutions of water management to avoid such flood situations in the future and also to observe the spatial analysis of the flood to optimize the mitigations measures.

Methodology

The following methodology describes the overall research strategy of the study and the research processes in Figure 1. The process encompasses data collection, data cleaning, field visits with testing (Soil test and Infiltration test), and eventually the simulations are performed using the HEC-RAS 5.0 integrated with GIS techniques.

Study area

The study area, Pasakha, is approximately 17 km from Phuentsholing, which is considered to be the first location for the establishment of a major industrial town under Chukha dzongkhag. It is located in the southern part of Bhutan at the latitude of $26^{\circ} 50' 42.28''$ and longitude of $89^{\circ} 27' 14.39$ roughly 319 m above M.S.L. (mean sea level) as depicted in Figure 2a and 2b. This place is very much viable to climate change and capable enough to be influenced by Indian industrial activities located at the border of India, Jaigaon being the border to Bhutan, being all the time bustling with lots of commercial activities, similar to many other West Bengal centers of commerce.

The study area has been popular as a location for different industries that were established since the 1990s and presently there are many industries such as – Bhutan carbide and chemicals (BCCL), Bhutan ferroalloys limited (BFAL), Tashi carbon as depicted in Figure 3. The other

recent expanded factories are the Druk cement plant and Bhutan board products limited (BBPL).

Figure 1: Summary flowchart of adopted research methodology

The most recent establishment is the Bhutan Beverages Company limited (BBCL), a soft drink bottling plant that belongs to Tashi Group that began commercial production. Aside from those, several small and medium industries were set up in the last few years, and thus growth of industries has been significantly noticeable at Pasakha. The flooding of the Barsa River has always been a huge threat to them and had damaged several residential areas, telecommunication and power lines, and even some of the factories due to the past year's floods.

Figure 2: (a) Elevation variation map (Chukha district) (b) Study area with Barsa River

Figure 3: Factories along the study area

Basin modeling in ArcGIS 9.3

Pasakha river basin was delineated from Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) of Terra satellite (<http://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov>) of resolution to be fed to ArcGIS 9.3 processing. Terrain processing and basin modeling was conducted in ArcGIS to obtain the drainage pattern and characteristics of the physical watershed area. Land use map was obtained from Toposheet 78F05 (1:50000) and Pasakha Base map (CAD data) as depicted in Figure. 4. High-resolution Google Earth Images were engaged to generate the land use/cover map of the study area. The generated maps were geo-referenced and processed the mosaicking to combine precisely, to get the most recent pattern of land-use/cover alteration which can be generated through the integration with GIS techniques. The generated features have been projected in DrukRef 03 local grid Chhukha_TM for the security point of view. Moreover, CAD data can accurately highlight features such as buildings, built-up structures, open spaces, paved parking, roads, and walkways. Besides, it is also been integrated with small features of agricultural land but the majority are forest cover along the path of river flow in the study area.

The basin is 53.13 sq. km and is divided into 4 sub-basins based on drainage pattern, where sub-basin W460 includes the majority of urban features in the area. Elevation ranges from a minimum of 280 m to a maximum of 1800 m above M.S.L. in the study area (Figure 4b). It is been recorded that plentiful rainfall occurs from June through October during the monsoon season averaging to an annual rainfall of 4000-5000 mm which is considered to be uniformly consistent in the studied area. Based on the map being generated, there are only two categories of Hydrologic soil group (HSG) i.e. HSG A and HSG B that predominantly covered the area.

Figure 4: (a) Location of study area (b) Five Sub-Basins by HEC_HMS

Hydrologic Soil Group (HSG) map was prepared after conducting a standard number of infiltration tests in each sub-basin per the size of the area to maintain uniformity over the study area. The infiltration rates have been categorized under the HSG classification system. Based on the infiltration rate value, the soil category of numerical values was assigned to integrate HSG A and HSG B soil which is allocated as 1 and 2 respectively. The assigned values were used to interpolate through various interpolation methods such as Universal Kriging, IDW, and Ordinary Kriging. To validate and check the accuracy of the results generated through these methods, interpolation methods were adopted by piloting several infiltration tests according to the size of the study area. It has been suitably illustrated that the Universal Kriging interpolation method reacted well with the authenticated results.

Soil grouping: Infiltration testing

The infiltration rate for each soil group for a specific area is stipulated in the TR-55 manual developed by NRCS, USDA. For study along Barsa river in the watershed of Barsa river, Double Ring Infiltrometer tests were conducted as per ASTM D5093 code. Table 1 indicates the selected CN value of the Hydrologic soil group (HSG) by infiltrations test.

Figure 5: Double Infiltration Test at the field

The soil was grouped based on the result obtained from the infiltrations at the site and then comparing with the HSG Classification Table 1. As per the result obtained at the site, the soil at the study area was grouped as A and B. Soil around the industries and colony area was grouped as A (W460 and W500), and the upstream area was grouped as B. There was an increase in infiltration above 0.3 in/hr in group A. As it moves upstream of the river, infiltration decreases to less than 0.3 in/hr (grouped B) as shown in Table 1.

Hydrologic soil group (HSG)

The land use/cover map was generated along with the HSG map to calculate the runoff water, CN values were appropriately determined assuming type 2 antecedent moisture condition (AMC-II) so that the CN map could be interpolated to the study area using (TR-55 manual). CN zonation ranges from 0 to 100, wherein, greater CN zoning value represents higher runoff and low infiltration, vis-à-vis, lower CN zoning value represents low runoff and high infiltration.

Curve Number

The SCS-CN method strategy was adopted to decide the various factors to check with TR-55 value:

$$Q = (P - I_a) 2 / (P - I_a) + S$$

The value of Q, P, and I_a are measured of runoff in mm, depth of rainfall in mm, and the initial abstraction in mm, respectively:

$$I_a = 0.2S$$

$$S = (25,400/CN) - 254$$

CN-curve number and S value are considered as potential maximum retention that later runoff initiates (USDA, 1972). The following equation is adopted to determine the discharge value:

$$Q = (P - 0.2S) 2 / (P + 0.8S)$$

Based on soil hydrologic conditions, curve numbers were assigned to each of the sub-basin to calculate the discharge and area of each basin. The discharge determination was then processed through HEC-HMS following the curve number.

Table 1: Curve Number assigned to Sub-basin

Sub basin notation	Hydrologic Soil Group	Area (km ²)	CN
W350	A	21.48	30
W430	A	11.8	30
W500	B	4.65	55
W460	B	15.2	55

Runoff simulation in HEC HMS 3.4

Here, the HEC-HMS 3.4 was employed to determine the surface runoff through simulation in each sub-basin considering no presence of base flow (Figure 6). This simulation has been performed only for the monsoon period. SCS unit hydrograph processes were engaged to compute the Time of Concentration, (T_c in hours) involving the formula below:

$$T_c = L^{0.8} [(1000 * CN) - 9]^{0.7} / 4407 (Sg)^{0.5}$$

This L is considered to be the lengthiest flow path (m), CN-weighted Curve Number, Sg is the average slope of the basin. Lag time (in hours) is determined using the formula indicating each sub-basin detail in Table 2.

$$T_L = 0.6 T_C$$

Figure 6 indicates the summarized outcomes of the depth, base flow, and precipitation loss and outflow of one the sub-basin and it is exhibited for W350 which supersedes the discharges over other Sub-basin.

Figure 6: The summarized outcome of runoff after precipitation

Table 2: Result of HEC-HMS

Hydrologic Element	Drainage area (km ²)	Peak discharge (m ³ /s)	Volume (m ³)
W350	21.48	11.60	41760
W430	11.79	6.40	23040
W500	4.64	2.70	9720
W460	15.19	8.80	31680
Outlet	53.12	29.50	106200

Hydrology data (peak discharge of debris flow at the outlet)

A flow that is generally created by the debris with huge sediment contained in it forming a moraine dam and flowing to the downstream containing huge energy is called a debris flow. This flow which is considered a peak discharge is determined based on record events such as a catastrophe triggered in the year 2000 releasing a huge amount of water volume from an artificial reservoir upstream. The characteristics of such reservoirs are calculated depending on the hypsometry of the reservoir, the height of the reservoir, width, and the texture of the moraine wall as indicated in Figure 7. Additionally, characteristics of downstream topography, and the amount of sediment deposited in the river basin below the artificial dam can trigger the nature of the flow. The peak flood of such nature can be determined using the critical wave method as successfully estimated in many hydraulics types of research.

Peak debris-flow discharge (Q_{max}^d) is the total calculated amount of water discharge and the entrained sediment as follows:

$$Q_{max}^d = Kq_m - (\text{complete failure})$$

$$Q_{max}^d = KQ_m \text{ (partial failure)}$$

The q_m and Q_{max} are the peak flood discharge at an outlet, k coefficient of debris flow discharge as given below:

$$k = 1 + \frac{\gamma_d - \gamma_w}{\gamma_s - \gamma_d}$$

The assumed value of γ_d is the debris flow density (kN/m^3), $\gamma_w = 10 \text{ kN/m}^3$ the density of water, and $\gamma_s = 26.5\text{--}27.5 \text{ kN/m}^3$ (density of solid grains in the debris flow). The following peak discharge flow is as:

$$q_m = \lambda B \sqrt{g} H_1^{3/2}$$

Figure 7: Sketches of gully cross-section of artificial dam location

Where B_x is the width of the dam after the outburst of a flood, B is the width before the failure (Figure 7); H_x height of dam after outburst; H_1 is the overall height before failure/outburst as shown Figure 9.

The overall discharge of the flood is dependent on the height of the dam which is related to the height at the upper portion and lower portion of the outlet synchronized by the shapes and the channel size formed during the outburst. Hence, the discharge determination adopting the critical wave method is fully dependent on the types of dam failures or outbursts such as rapid complete failure, rapid partial failure, and gradual failure (Chen et al., 2007). The calculation methods for the first two types of failure. Table 3 indicates the amount of water stored in the artificial dam, this amount (1713.48 cumecs) along with the cross-section of the river was taken as an input for the HEC-RAS modeling assuming the record. The HEC-RAS tool was integrated into the GIS tool for the generation of Flood Modeling.

Table 3: Parameters and discharge input in HEC_RAS

Lamda (λ)	B (m)	g	H1 (m)	q_m	K	Q_{max} (Cumec)
0.173	50	9.81	10	856.74	2	1713.48

Hydraulics data

In general, there are two methods of exacting the cross-sections, one is surveying at the site engaging in surveying equipment's which can be generated eventually in AutoCAD. HEC-GeoRAS was engaged to generate the cross-sections of the river as indicated in Figure 8. It is a set of procedures, tools, and utilities for processing geospatial data in ArcGIS. This software was initially developed by the US Army Corps of Engineers. The extracted cross-sections were fed as an input for the modeling in HEC-RAS 5.0. This study attempts to utilize both the methods to validate one to another data sets and some of the cross-sections generated from

software are put to correction tallying with the physical surveying data set. After rectifying and cleaning the cross-sections, simulation were performed using HEC_RAS 5.0 software which is an extension tool in ArcGIS.

Figure 8: Cross-sections of River (HEC-GeoRAS)

Results and Discussion

Flood modeling results

This study analyzed the flood risk assessment basically to recognize the most potential flooding area that can potentially affect the residential and industries areas. Based on the results, an appropriate and timely strategy can be adopted by the concerned planners and disaster mitigations management. The results of the flood level will guide the planners for the zonation of the area for the upcoming infrastructure development activities. Figure 11 indicates the depth and expansion of flood during the peak discharge released when the combined discharge of reservoirs (moraine dam) and the run-off volume act simultaneously. The highest velocity (45m/s) area indicated by blue and red-colored indicates the lowest velocity as the flow approaches the plain area in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Variation of velocity at different locations

To generate the flood modeling, the inputs factors are cross-sections of the river including left and right bank locations, roughness coefficients or Manning’s coefficients assumed a 0.04 uniform throughout based on the nature of the river system of Bhutan. The HEC-RAS integrated with the GIS model was then used to develop a floodplain resulting in an approximately 45 m depth which indicated as the highest during the peak flood (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Variation of depths of River

Flood hazard mapping is considered to be the most appropriate technique for the urban planners to decide on developmental activities as these maps give an idea of the future consequences and can be prioritized for the mitigation of risk areas (Bapalu and Sinha, 2005). This research attempted to develop the methodology to identify the risk area by delineating potential flood areas of the Pasakha region using a Geographic Information System (GIS) environment as in Figure 11. Based on the result generated from the simulation, Table 6 indicates the approximate area that will be flooded spilling the discharge away from the natural bank of the river if the calculated amount of discharge happens to outburst at any time. However, only the runoff generated discharge from the rainfall will not have any magnitude of disaster flood at least for decades in the Pasakha region

Figure 11: Different areas under the influence of flood if a discharge of 1742.98 cumecs outbursts

The Table 4 shows the total area under the influence of flood that is going to be affected by the calculated discharge. Based on the simulation, there are 4 major areas possible be affected, a total of 48.15 acres (Table 4; Figure 12). Those affected areas were validated by visiting the real ground places.

Table 4: Different risk zoning areas under the influence of flood

Risk Area	Perimeter (m)	Influence of Flood (m ²)	Remarks
Area_1	252	2156.75	Near Canteen (BFAL)
Area_2	880	10545.41	Near Substation area
Area_3	2444.6	101096.55	BFAL Colony area
Area_4	1490	81047.98	Beer Factory area
Total	5,066.60	194846.69	
	Total area (m²)	389693.38	48.15 acres

Figure 12: Modeled flood area for the selected risk zoning areas

Conclusion

This paper studies the hydrological characteristics of the ungauged Basra River in Pasakha, Bhutan. With certain assumptions of hydrological parameters and the process, the modeling has been implemented using the SCS-CN method in HEC-HMS. The surface runoff volume after knowing the infiltration rate of the basin was determined. To execute a better planning strategy, proper water management needs to be adopted appropriately. Based on the results obtained through the study, some of the specific conclusions are provided below.

- 1) The result of this paper can be utilized for proper hydrology activities, to maintain a balance between runoff and infiltration rate. It may lead to the mapping of the meteorological and hydrological data in combine.

- 2) As for the Pasakha industrial area, where the majority of the industries are located nearby the river, a higher degree of attention should be given to river training works and drainage works for sustainable construction works and development.
- 3) Based on the nature of the watershed area, Universal Kriging/Ordinary Kriging are most suitable. Furthermore, with the help of conducted validated infiltration results, the accuracy of the Universal Kriging interpolation method can be adopted.
- 4) The HEC-HMS simulation has been completed to estimate the real-time surface runoff using the CN index value based on the infiltration rate. This study effectively calculated the surface runoff from four sub-basin averaging 7.37 m³/s that may not be of potential to flood the river.
- 5) Based on flood modeling results, four major areas would be under the influence of flood with a total area of 48.15 acres based on the moraine debris dam volume. The maximum velocity has been approximately 45m/s and the maximum depth about 45 m.
- 6) Mitigations measures need to be planned to align with the risk areas identified in the study.

References

- Bapalu, G. V., Sinha, R. (2005): GIS in Flood Hazard Mapping: A Case Study of Kosi River Basin, India. *GIS Development Weekly* 1(13): 1-3.
- Burt, T., Bates, P., Stewart, M., Claxton, A., Anderson, M., Price, D. (2002): Water Table Fluctuations within the Floodplain of the River Severn, England. *Journal of Hydrology* 262(1-4): 1-20.
- Chen, X.Q., Cui, P., Chen, N.S., Gardner, J. (2007): Calculation of discharge of debris flows caused by moraine-dam failure at Midui Gully, Tibet, China. *Iranian Journal of Science & Technology, Transaction B, Engineering* 31(B2): 195-207
- Cronshey, R., McCuen, R.H., Miller, N., Rawls, W., Robbins, S., Woodward, D. (1986): Urban Hydrology for Small Watersheds. In: Technical Report 55. Natural Resources Conservation Service, United States Department of Agriculture, Washington, D.C.
- Dhawale, W. A. (2013): Runoff Estimation for Darewadi Watershed using RS and GIS. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering* 1(6): 46-50.
- DMSG (2001):The use of Earth Observing Satellite for Hazard support: Assessment and Scenarios. In: Committee on Earth Observation Satellites Disaster Management Support Group, final report. NOAA, Dept, Commerce, USA.
- Elhakeem, M., Papanicolaou, A. N. (2009): Estimation of the Runoff Curve Number via direct rainfall simulator measurements in the State of Iowa, USA. *Water Resources Management* 23(12): 2455-2473.
- Forkuo, E. K. (2011): Digital Elevation Modelling using ASTER Stereo Imagery. *Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering* 52(2): 81-92.
- Gruntfest, E., Handmer, J. (2001). Dealing with flash floods: contemporary issues and future possibilities. In: *Coping with flash floods*. Springer, Dordrecht: 3-10.
- Ikhuria, I., Yesuf, G., Enaruvbe, G. O., Ige-Olumide, O. (2012): Assessment of the impact of flooding on farming communities in Nigeria: A case study of Lokoja, Kogi State Nigeria. /Conference held at Regional Centre for Training in Aerospace Surveys (RECTAS), Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, 19th–22nd November 2012: 156-167.

- Seyedeh, S. S., Thamer, A. M., Mahmud, A. R. B., Majid, K. K., Amir, S. (2008): Integrated Modelling for Flood Hazard Mapping Using Watershed Modelling System, *American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* 1(2): 149-156.
- Soulis, K., Valiantzas, J., Dercas, N., Londra, P. (2009): Investigation of the direct runoff generation mechanism for the analysis of the SCS-CN method applicability to a partial area experimental watershed, *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 13(05): 605-615.
- Tekeli, I.Y., Akgul, S., Dengiz, O., Akuzum, T. (2007): Estimation of flood discharge for small watershed using SCS curve number and Geographic Information System. *International Congress on River Basin Management*: 527-538.
- USDA Soil Conservation Service: (1972): Hydrology. In: Section 4, Soil Conservation Service National Engineering Handbook, U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington, DC.